

Insects in an introduced double-cropping pattern of rainfed lowland rice

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A single rice crop transplanted in July is the traditional cropping pattern at the research site of the IRRI-Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry Cropping Systems Program in Oton and Tigbauan, Iloilo, Philippines. The IRRI-BPI team is testing the feasibility of double-cropping of rice by establishing the first crop with the onset of the rainy season (usually in May) after a 3-month dry fallow period. If farmers grow early maturing varieties, there is sufficient rainfall in this non-irrigated area to plant a second rice crop.

Insect pests were monitored in plots that had been treated with insecticide and in untreated plots in six farmers' fields where two crops of IR28 were grown in the introduced pattern. The first crop was wet-seeded in May and the second was transplanted in October.

The first crop was essentially insect free; both protected and unprotected plots yielded 5.1 t/ha (see table). Because the crop was established early with the first rains, it escaped pest buildup. The second crop was attacked by the same insect complex that normally attacks the single rice crop. The key insects were rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* (whose larvae defoliate the crop), rice green-homed caterpillar *Melanitis leda ismene*, and rice skipper *Pelopidas mathias*. Minor insects were stem borers (predominantly white rice borer *Scirpophaga innotata*) and rice bug *Leptocorisa oratorius*. The pests increased on the first rice crop as well as on the grassy weeds that proliferated in fallow fields with the onset of rains before the July puddling of the single crop. The yield protected and unprotected plots difference between the insecticide-(5.0 vs 3.9 t/ha) was significant in the second crop. The fact that the first crop requires no insect control makes the double-rice pattern attractive to farmers whose cash resources to purchase insecticides are limited.

Insect occurrence and benefit from insecticide protection on the first (wet-seeded IR28) and second (transplanted IR28) crops of an introduced rice double-cropping pattern in a rainfed lowland environment. Oton and Tigbauan, Iloilo, Philippines, 1976.						
Crop	Defoliation (%)	Stemborer (%)		Rice bugs (no/m ²)	Yield (t/ha)	
		Deadhearts	Whiteheads		Untreated plots	Treated plots ^{a/}
First ^{b/}	4	2.6	2.3	1.2	5.1	5.1
Second ^{c/}	22	5.4	7.4	3.7	3.9	5.0

^{a/} 2 kg a.i. carbofuran (Furadan 3G)/ha incorporated in the soil before planting, followed by 4 spray applications of 0.75 kg a.i. monocrotophos (Azodrin 16.8 EC)/ha

^{b/} Av. of 6 fields planting in May

^{c/} Av. of 6 fields planted in October

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